

Spectrophotometric Study of Malate Complexes of Copper and Aluminium

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The instability constant of the (1:1) copper (II)-malate complex at pH 4.0 and ionic strength 1.0 is found to be 3.74×10^{-4} at 27-30° from spectrophotometric measurements. Using this complex as the indicator in the displacement method, the aluminium-malate has been shown to be a 1:1 complex. The instability constant of the aluminium complex is 4.84×10^{-4} at the same temperature, pH, and ionic strength.

The malate complex of copper(II) was first reported by Delsal¹ from electrometric measurements. Lefebvre and Souchay² and Nanda and Pani³ studied this complex by pH titrations. No spectrophotometric study has, however, been reported. We report herein a spectrophotometric study on copper-malate complex. Using this coloured complex as the indicator species in the displacement method, we have determined the nature of the aluminium-malate complex and also its stability constant. Tsintsevich *et al.*⁴ report that the stability of the malate complex of aluminium increases with the increase of pH and a maximum is attained in the pH range of 7.0 to 8.0. They, however, reported no estimate of the stability constant.

EXPERIMENTAL

The chemicals used were of AnalaR quality. Copper perchlorate was prepared by dissolving copper carbonate in warm dilute perchloric acid. Aluminium perchlorate was prepared according to Nanda and Aditya⁵. Sodium perchlorate was used to maintain the ionic strength.

All measurements of optical densities were taken with a Hilger and Watt 'Uvispek' spectrophotometer with a quartz prism. Matched glass cells of 10, 20, and 30 mm optical path were used, depending on the concentration of the solutions. The slit width was always maintained at 0.02 mm. All the measurements were taken at the room temperature (27—30°). The optical densities were measured at 750, 770, and 800 m μ , interchanging the cells to avoid any error due to cells getting dirty during the course of measurement. The pH measurements were taken with a Marconi battery operated pH-meter, model T.F.511D.

1. *J. chim. phys.*, 1938, **34**, 314.
2. *Compt. rend.*, 1958, **243**, 1416.
3. *This Journal*, 1958, **35**, 355.
4. *Zhur., Obsh. Khim.*, 1958, **13**, 221.
5. *This Journal*, 1957, **34**, 557.

For studying the copper-malate system, copper perchlorate and malic acid were mixed, the *pH* being adjusted by adding the required amount of acid or alkali (previously determined by *pH* titration) and the ionic strength, by adding sodium perchlorate. For the aluminium-malate system, in addition to those mentioned above, aluminium perchlorate was also added before making up the volume.

DISCUSSION

Copper-Malate Complex

The change in absorption of copper perchlorate on addition of malic acid indicates the formation of a complex. At *pH* 4.0, a maximum in absorption appears around 760 $m\mu$ (in case of copper perchlorate solution the absorption goes on increasing beyond 800 $m\mu$). This change in absorption has been utilised in determining the molecular composition of the complex, using continued variation method. The Job's curves were run at 750, 770, and 800 $m\mu$ and at *pH* 4.0 and for two different total molarities, namely, 0.02 and 0.04 *M*. $\bar{D}$, the difference of the optical densities of the mixture of copper perchlorate and malic acid solutions and that of copper perchlorate solution alone, was plotted against the mole fraction of copper. The curves had maxima at mole fraction of 0.5, indicating the formation of the complex containing copper (II) and malic acid in the ratio of 1:1.

The molar extinction coefficient of copper-malate complex was determined from the optical density of copper perchlorate solution containing a large excess of malic acid, when all the copper could be assumed to be in the form of complex. The extinction coefficients at *pH* 4.0 and wave lengths 750, 770, and 800 $m\mu$ are 27.24 ± 0.08 , 27.87 ± 0.08 , and 27.77 ± 0.08 , respectively. The corresponding extinction coefficients of only copper perchlorate solution are 9.91 ± 0.01 , 10.96 ± 0.12 , and 11.70 ± 0.06 .

The continued variation method indicates the formation of 1:1 complex. So, for the determination of the stability constant of the complex, solutions were prepared containing nearly equal concentrations of copper perchlorate and malic acid and optical density was measured. The stability constant was calculated in the same way as done by Nanda and Aditya⁵, *K* being equal to $\frac{[\text{Cu}^{2+}][\text{H}_2\text{L}]}{[\text{CuL}]}$ for the equilibrium:

(where H_2L represents malic acid), since the *pH* is constant. The results are recorded in Table I. The average instability constant is 3.74×10^{-4} .

Nanda and Pani represented *K* as the instability constant, taking the hydrogen-ion concentration in it, e.g., $K = [\text{CuL}][\text{H}^+]^2 / [\text{Cu}^{2+}][\text{H}_2\text{L}]$. On this basis our value is 2.67×10^{-5} which is slightly different from 3.89×10^{-5} by Nanda and Pani⁵.

This small difference may be due to the following: (i) The ionic strength of the medium used by Nanda and Pani⁵ was 0.25, whereas we have maintained it at 1.0.

(ii) They⁵ used potassium nitrate for maintaining the ionic strength and copper sulphate. Sulphate and nitrate ions are known to form complexes with copper ion⁶. A similar

discrepancy has been noted by Nanda and Aditya⁵ on comparing their values for the stability constant for aluminium-sulphosalicylate complex with those reported by Lasater and Anderson⁷, who used aluminium sulphate and sodium sulphate for adjusting the ionic strength.

TABLE I

Instability constant of copper-malate complex.
Ionic strength = 1.0. pH = 4.0. Cell length = 10 mm.

Cu (ClO ₄) ₂ × 10 ² M.	Malic acid × 10 ² M.	Average O. D.	Instability const. × 10 ⁴ .	Average instability const. × 10 ⁴ M.
A. Wave length = 750 mμ.				
1.5	1.5	0.451	3.44	
1.6	1.6	0.490	5.03	
1.6	2.0	0.436	2.65	
1.7	1.7	0.522	5.66	4.25(±0.45)
1.7	2.2	0.578	4.48	
1.8	1.2	0.476	2.68	
2.0	2.5	0.670	5.83	
2.0	2.0	0.643	5.33	
B. Wave length = 770 mμ.				
1.5	1.5	0.453	2.42	
1.6	2.0	0.440	4.19	
1.7	1.7	0.521	3.93	
1.8	1.2	0.477	4.01	3.46(±0.27)
1.9	1.6	0.560	3.29	
2.0	2.5	0.663	2.92	
C. Wave length = 800 mμ.				
1.5	2.0	0.403	2.55	
1.6	2.0	0.423	2.44	
1.7	2.2	0.500	3.00	
1.8	1.8	0.513	3.58	3.50(±0.48)
1.8	1.2	0.457	5.79	
2.0	2.0	0.597	3.66	

Average instability constant = $3.74 \times 10^{-4} M$.

Aluminium-malate Complex

When aluminium perchlorate is added to a solution of copper malate, the colour fades. This decrease in colour has been utilised in determining composition of the complex and also the instability constant.

The molecular composition of the complex of aluminium and malic acid has been determined at pH 4.0 and an ionic strength 1.0 by an indirect application of Job's method.

7. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 1423.

Two sets of solutions were prepared. The first set was prepared by mixing aluminium perchlorate and malic acid in varying proportions, keeping the total molarity fixed (in the present case 0.02 *M*) and adding copper perchlorate equivalent to the malic acid. The blank set contained equivalent amounts of copper perchlorate and malic acid. The difference of absorbances of the corresponding solutions was plotted against the mole fraction of Al^{3+} ion. The curve has a minimum at ≈ 0.5 , which shows that complex contains Al^{3+} ion and malate ion in the ratio of 1:1 (Fig. 1).

FIG. 1

For determining the instability constant of the aluminium complex, optical densities of solutions, containing copper perchlorate, aluminium perchlorate, and malic acid, with *pH* adjusted to 4.0 and ionic strength to 1.0, were measured. The results are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Instability constant of aluminium-malate complex.

Ionic strength = 1.0. *pH* = 4.0. Cell = 20 mm length. Wave length = 750 μ .

$\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \times 10^2 M.$	Malic acid $\times 10^2 M.$	$\text{Al}(\text{ClO}_4)_3 \times 10^2 M.$	Average O.D.	Instability const. $\times 10^4.$
1.5	1.5	1.5	0.542	4.34
1.5	2.0	1.5	0.633	5.43
1.6	1.6	1.6	0.590	5.16
1.7	1.7	1.7	0.618	4.50
1.6	1.2	1.2	0.540	4.18
1.7	2.0	2.0	0.643	4.68
1.8	1.8	1.8	0.655	4.97
1.8	1.5	1.8	0.620	5.45

Average instability constant = $4.84 (\pm 0.16) \times 10^{-4} M.$

For the solutions, we have;

$$D(\text{optical density})/l = \epsilon_1 [\text{Cu}^{2+}]_{\text{free}} + \epsilon_2 [\text{CuL}]$$

where ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 are the extinction coefficients of Cu^{2+} ion and copper malate complex respectively and *l*, the cell length,

$$[\text{Cu}^{2+}]_{\text{total}} = [\text{Cu}^{2+}]_{\text{free}} + [\text{CuL}],$$

$$[\text{Al}^{3+}]_{\text{total}} = [\text{Al}^{3+}]_{\text{free}} + [\text{AlL}],$$

$$[\text{H}_2\text{L}]_{\text{total}} = [\text{H}_2\text{L}]_{\text{free}} + (\text{AlL}) + [\text{CuL}].$$

and

$$K_{\text{inst. (CuL)}} = [\text{Cu}^{2+}] [\text{L}] / [\text{CuL}]$$

at fixed *pH*. Using these equations, $[\text{Al}^{3+}]_{\text{free}}$, $[\text{AlL}]$, and $[\text{H}_2\text{L}]_{\text{free}}$ are calculated.

Representing the equilibrium for the aluminium complex as

the equilibrium constant, at *pH* 4.0, which is given by the expression;

$$K = [\text{Al}^{3+}] [\text{L}] / [\text{AlL}]$$

at constant ionic strength, has been calculated.

The values of the instability constant are shown in column 5 of Table II. The average value of the instability constant of the aluminium-malate complex is 4.84×10^{-4} . This is equivalent to 2.06×10^{-3} for the stability constant incorporating the hydrogen ion concentration.

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